

Food-Grade Vitamin a Nanoemulsion: A Strategy for Nutrient Fortification and Sensory Enhancement

Somya Khanna ^{1*}, Pragati Singh ¹, Ekta Singh Chauhan ²

^{1*,1} Research Scholar, Department of Food Science and Nutrition, Banasthali Vidyapith, Tonk, Rajasthan-304022, India

² Associate Professor, Department of Food Science and Nutrition, Banasthali Vidyapith, Tonk, Rajasthan-304022, India

Received: Jul 20, 2025

Accepted: Aug 20, 2025

Published: Aug 26, 2025

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to acknowledge the staff of Krishi Vigyan Kendra of Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India, for their support in the identification of the guava variety. We also want to give special thanks to Mr. Vimal Jain for giving us technological knowledge during our experiment.

Fundings

No funding provided from any source

Abstract

Fortification of food and beverages with vitamin A is demanding due to its poor water solubility, oxidation and due to exposure to light and high temperature. The aim of this research work was to formulate an effective food-grade delivery system for the incorporation of vitamin A into food products and beverages. The formulation of food-grade vitamin A nanoemulsion was successfully prepared using mixed surfactant (Tween 80 and soya lecithin) in a 3:1 ratio and ultrasonic homogenization techniques for choosing the most stable formulation and to check the vitamin A efficiency entrapment. The results showed that the droplet sizes of the nanoemulsion was 131.4 ± 0.2 and 131.8 ± 0.1 nm on the 1st and 30th day, respectively, with the droplet growth ratio of 0.00304 and PDI score of 0.213 ± 0.003 showing the stability of the nanoemulsion and uniformity in the droplet size distribution. At the end of 30 days of storage, the efficiency entrapment of vitamin A of the most stable nanoemulsion was $87.5 \pm 0.97\%$ which was then incorporated in the variants of chakli. The sensory evaluation of the developed food products showed that variant A was most acceptable, in which all-purpose flour was enriched with Bengal gram dal flour, flaxseed flour and sesame seeds and the incorporation of different flours and vitamin A nanoemulsion helped in increasing the nutritive value of the variants and enhanced the vitamin A. These results suggest that mixed surfactant-based nanoemulsions are an effective delivery system for the incorporation of vitamin A into food and beverages to overcome the worldwide deficiency of vitamin A.

Keywords: Nanoemulsion, Nanoencapsulation, Incorporation, Vitamin A, Chakli

1. Introduction

The food is considered the primary need of humans and with the passing years, the use of technology in food industries helps in improving its taste, odour, shelf life, nutritive value, bioavailability and safety (Hassan ME et al., 2021). The application of technology in the food industry is playing an effective role in making enriched food products, which can lead to the reduction of diseases. In today's world, nanotechnology applications in the food industry are giving an effective result in improving food (Sahoo M et al., 2021). One of the

nanotechnologies used for making the food enrich is nanoemulsion for carrying various bioactives, vitamins, minerals, enzymes, etc (Samal D, 2017). Emulsion can be defined as a fine dispersion of two immiscible liquids of minute droplets that are insoluble. Water and oil are the two commonly used liquids for the formation of emulsions and nanoemulsions are emulsions having a small diameter under 200 nm (Elarbi FM et al., 2022). They are made up of an oil phase, a water phase and an emulsifier, in which the emulsifier plays an important role in creating small-sized particles by decreasing the surface energy per unit area between the oil and water phases of emulsion. They also improve the kinetic stability of the nanoemulsion. Many studies reveal that nanoemulsion helps in bio-accessibility of the lipid compounds (Das AK et al., 2020).

Generally, deficiency of vitamin A is very commonly seen among people, which is a leading cause of preventable blindness, particularly in children, and can also weaken the immune system. The main reason for its deficiency is its hydrophobic nature, which causes its low bioavailability in the body (Kundu S et al., 2021). Also, an easy degradation of vitamin A and its precursors is seen in food products due to light combinations, less solubility of water and oxidation which do not allow its straight distribution in aqueous solution, so it must include into colloidal delivery system and vitamin A infused nanoemulsion fortification in food products helps in better bio-accessibility of vitamin A in the body leading to control its deficiency (Mun S et al., 2015). This study aims to obtain enriched chakli to supply vitamin A among people to meet their nutritional and sensory needs.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials Required

Food-grade Vitamin A (Retinyl Acetate), Cold-pressed mustard oil, Tween 80, and Soy lecithin were obtained from HiMedia Laboratories Private Limited, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India, and Distilled water was used for preparing a nanoemulsion. For preparing the food product, i.e., Chakli, all the ingredients required were purchased from the local market of Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India. A total of 4 samples were prepared, of which one was standard with no manipulations and the remaining 3 were the variants were different compositions and nanoencapsulated vitamin A nanoemulsion. The ingredients and amount used are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of different samples of chakli

Ingredients	Standard	Variant A	Variant B	Variant C
All-purpose Flour (g)	85	42	42	42
Maize Flour (g)	-	-	37	-
Black gram dal Flour (g)	-	37	-	-
Buckwheat Flour (g)	-	-	-	37
Flaxseed Flour (g)	-	2	2	2
Sesame seeds (g)	-	2	2	2
Butter (g)	15	15	15	15
Salt	To taste	To taste	To taste	To taste
Cumin Seeds	To taste	To taste	To taste	To taste
Red Chilli Powder	To taste	To taste	To taste	To taste

Vitamin-A Nanoencapsulated Nanoemulsion (g)	Not Incorporated	2	2	2
---	---------------------	---	---	---

2.2 Preparation of nanoemulsion

In this study, oil-in-water nanoemulsion was prepared, in which aqueous was the continuous phase and oil was the dispersed phase. For making nanoemulsion, tween 80 (surfactant) and soy lecithin (co-surfactant) were used in the ratio of 3:1. The vitamin A of 2g was dissolved in 100g of mustard oil using a magnetic stirrer. Then, 5g of vitamin A infused mustard oil was added in the formulation of 100g of nanoemulsion. Then, the continuous phase mixture was homogenized at 4000 rpm for 30 minutes and vitamin A infused mustard oil was added drop by drop to the continuous phase, followed by 30 minutes of probe sonication at 20 kHz at a temperature of 40°C, leading to the formation of a nanoemulsion. The temperature rise during sonication was controlled using an ice bath. The ratio of surfactant to oil phase (S/O) used in the formulation of nanoemulsion is shown in Table 2. The droplet size and PDI of nanoemulsion were analysed using Zetasizer and were stored at 5°C for 24 hours for the incorporation in chakli.

Table 2: Composition of Nanoemulsion

Surfactant /Oil Ratio	Oil phase	Total surfactant	Surfactant 1	Surfactant 2	Vitamin A	Aqueous phase
0.3	5 g	1.5 g	1.125 g	0.375 g	0.2 g	93.5 g

2.3 Characterization of nanoemulsion

2.3.1 Determination of droplet size

The droplet size of nanoemulsions plays an important role in how well they work. Smaller droplets have more surface area and are usually more stable, which is helpful in products like medicines and food (Mehmood et al., 2019; Mehmood, 2015). The average droplet size of all nanoemulsions was checked using a Zetasizer (Malvern Zetasizer Nano) through dynamic light scattering.

2.3.2 Droplet growth ratio (DGR)

Nanoemulsions can sometimes form larger droplets when stored, so their stability was tested by checking if the particle size increased over time. The size of the particles was measured right after preparation and again after 30 days. These measurements were then used to work out the particle growth ratio for each nanoemulsion (Mehmood et al., 2019; Mehmood, 2015). The ratio was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Droplet growth ratio (\%)} = \frac{\text{Size of the droplet (day 30)} - \text{Size of the droplet (day 1)}}{\text{Size of the droplet (day 1)}} \times 100$$

2.3.3 Polydispersity index (PDI)

The polydispersity index (PDI) shows how evenly the droplet sizes are distributed in a nanoemulsion. A low PDI means the droplets are mostly the same size, indicating a uniform

and stable system, while a high PDI means there is a wider range of droplet sizes, which can lead to instability. The PDI of all nanoemulsions was measured using dynamic light scattering with a Malvern Zetasizer Nano (Jun et al., 2021).

2.3.4 Entrapment efficiency (EE%)

Entrapment efficiency is the percentage of vitamin A successfully enclosed within the nanoemulsion droplets compared to the total amount initially added. In vitamin A nanoemulsions, a higher entrapment efficiency indicates better protection of the nutrient, controlled release, and improved absorption in the body.

To determine this, a slightly modified method from Khalid et al. (2016) was followed. One millilitre of the nanoemulsion was mixed with nine millilitres of ethanol and sonicated in an ice bath for 15 minutes. The mixture was then centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 30 minutes. The clear liquid on top (supernatant) was collected, and its absorbance was measured at 310 nm, using ethanol as a blank. Afterwards, 1 mg of the supernatant was diluted five times in ethanol (final concentration range 0.01–0.1 mg/ml). A standard curve of absorbance versus concentration was prepared to obtain the linear regression coefficient.

The entrapment efficiency of the most stable vitamin A nanoemulsion was calculated using the following equation:

$$EE\% = \frac{\text{Weight of free vitamin - A}}{\text{Weight of encapsulated vitamin - A}} \times 100$$

2.4 Preparation of Vitamin A nanoencapsulated Chakli

The food product was developed by incorporating the vitamin A nanoencapsulated nanoemulsion. A total 4 samples were prepared, with different flour compositions and nanoemulsions. Standard was not incorporated with nanoemulsion, while variants A, B and C were nanoencapsulated with 2 g of vitamin A rich nanoemulsion. The process of preparing all the samples is similar, just by changing the composition and nanoemulsion addition and the process is as follows-

Step 1: The flours, ingredients used and nanoemulsion were mixed together according to sample compositions and dough was prepared by kneading it and hot water was used for kneading.

Step 2: The dough was kept for rest by covering it for 30 minutes at room temperature. Step 3: The chakli maker was taken and greased with the oil.

Step 4: The dough was placed inside the chakli maker and the pressure was applied to form the chakli shape.

Step 5: The chakli formed dough was fried in the oil and served/ presented.

2.5 Sensory Evaluation

The sensory evaluation of all the samples was conducted, for which 20 members were selected through the triangle test and then the attributes like color, taste, texture, odour and overall acceptability were analysed using a 9-point hedonic scale. All the panellists were semi-trained and were from the Department of Food Science and Nutrition, Banasthali Vidyapith. In this scale, the panellist tastes the food samples and rate them from 1 to 9 according to their senses, in “9” score denoting extremely like and “1 denoting extremely dislike.

2.6 Nutritional Analysis

The nutritional analysis of the prepared samples was conducted, in which moisture content was determined using the Air-oven method, ash using the Muffle furnace method, protein using the Micro-Kjeldahl method, fat using the Soxhlet apparatus, and carbohydrates using calculation by difference (Raghuramulu N et al. 2003) (AOAC, 1995). The minerals sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium analyses were done with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (NIN, 2003). The vitamin A content was determined using an HPLC method.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

All the results were expressed in mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was performed by using analysis of paired t-test. Differences with ($P < 0.05$) were considered significant as determined by the least significant difference (LSD).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Nanoemulsion characteristics

The vitamin A nanoencapsulated nanoemulsion showed a droplet size of 131.4 ± 0.2 and a PDI score of 0.00304, which shows good stability and uniform distribution of the droplets. The efficiency entrapment was observed at $87.5 \pm 0.97\%$. In this study, the results were compared with earlier research. Jun et al. (2021) found bigger droplet sizes, between 218.0 nm and 405.1 nm, with PDI values from 0.172 to 0.209 when using different surfactant ratios. On the other hand, Algahtani et al. (2020) reported much smaller droplets of 71.95 nm and a very low PDI of 0.015. Alvarez et al. (2020) tested two coating materials, where Capsul gave a droplet size of 102.5 nm with a PDI of 0.473, and sodium caseinate produced droplets of 100.4 nm with a PDI of 0.431. Boskabadi et al., (2021) observed 66.01%, Kim et al., (2019) documented 100%, Argimon et al., (2017) reported 90.7% of EE range.

3.2 Developed food product

The figure shows the developed food products in which the standard is normal without nanoemulsion and the other are variants with enriched flours and 2 g of nanoemulsion in each variant. Chakli was chosen for incorporation as it is one of the most common snacks eaten at every age.

Figure 1: Developed food products

3.3 Sensory evaluation

The sensory evaluation of the samples, i.e., standard, variant A, B and C is shown in Table 2. The results show that the standard had the highest colour acceptability, with 8.65 ± 0.48 , variant A was having highest taste acceptability with 8.90 ± 0.72 , standard had with highest texture acceptability with 7.85 ± 0.51 , variant A with highest odour and overall acceptability with 9.25 ± 0.55 and 9.550 ± 0.45 , respectively.

A paired t-test was conducted to analyze the sensory attributes of each variant of chakli compared to standard chakli. In variant A, a highly significant difference was seen in taste, odour, and overall acceptability, while a significant difference was observed in texture and no significant difference was observed in the appearance. In variant B, a highly significant difference was seen in odour, whereas a significant difference was observed in appearance, taste, texture, and overall acceptability. In variant C, a highly significant difference was seen in appearance and odour, while a significant difference was seen in the taste and overall acceptability, whereas no significant difference was observed in texture. The findings suggest that variant A was highly acceptable.

Table 2: Sensory evaluation of the developed food products

Attributes	Standard	Variant A	Variant B	Variant C
Appearance	8.65±0.48	8.15±0.67 ^{ns}	7.50±0.51*	7.30±0.57**
Taste	8.25±0.22	8.90±0.72**	8.00±0.64*	7.30±0.65*
Texture	7.85±0.51	7.65±0.58*	7.35±0.48*	6.35±0.81 ^{ns}
Odour	8.10±0.78	9.25±0.55**	7.40±0.50**	7.30±0.47**
Overall Acceptability	8.80±0.41	9.55±0.45**	7.55±0.60*	7.05±0.60*

Values are presented as means ± SD (n=3). Highly significant differences are denoted as ** (P < 0.001), significant differences are denoted as * (P < 0.05), while values marked with ^{ns} indicate no significant difference (P > 0.05)

Standard = 85 g all-purpose flour + 15 g butter	Variant A = 42 g all-purpose flour + 37 g black gram dal flour + 2 g flaxseed flour + 2 g sesame seeds + 15 g butter + 2 g nanoemulsion
Variant B = 42 g all-purpose flour + 37 g maize flour + 2 g flaxseed flour + 2 g sesame seeds + 15 g butter + 2 g nanoemulsion	Variant C = 42 g all-purpose flour + 37 g buckwheat flour + 2 g flaxseed flour + 2 g sesame seeds + 15 g butter + 2 g nanoemulsion

Figure 2: Sensory evaluation of food products

These results align with the findings of Sarkar et al. (2020), who reported that the incorporation of bioactive nanoemulsion in bakery products improved flavour and odour attributes due to the efficient dispersion of hydrophobic compounds, which enhanced aroma release. Similarly, Patel et al. (2021) observed that fortification of traditional snacks with legume and oilseed flours improved consumer perception of taste and nutritional value. The higher odour scores in Variant A may be attributed to the natural aroma of sesame seeds and the stability of

encapsulated vitamin A, which prevented oxidative off-flavours, consistent with observations by Almeida et al. (2019) on the role of encapsulation in maintaining sensory quality of fortified foods.

3.4 Nutritional analysis

The nutritive value of the samples is shown in Table 3 and is expressed in 100g. The moisture (g/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C are 9.81 ± 0.05 ; 8.45 ± 0.03 ; 8.67 ± 0.10 and 8.21 ± 0.08 , respectively, depicting the highest content in standard and the lowest in variant C. The ash (g/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C are 1.61 ± 0.04 ; 2.41 ± 0.03 ; 2.21 ± 0.05 and 1.91 ± 0.04 , respectively, indicating the highest content in variant A and the lowest in standard. The carbohydrate (g/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C was 53.34 ± 0.23 ; 58.54 ± 0.31 ; 55.01 ± 0.28 and 51.48 ± 0.46 , respectively, showing variant A to have the highest and variant C to have the lowest carbohydrate content. The protein (g/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C was 17.52 ± 0.34 ; 13.29 ± 0.37 ; 13.66 ± 0.44 and 14.04 ± 0.39 , respectively, showing standard to have the highest and variant A to have the lowest protein content. The fat (g/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C were 14.49 ± 0.12 ; 8.76 ± 0.28 ; 9.45 ± 0.23 , and 10.16 ± 0.34 , respectively, showing standard to have the highest and variant A to have the lowest fat content. The total fiber (g/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C was 9.08 ± 0.32 ; 8.42 ± 0.57 ; 8.74 ± 0.22 and 8.86 ± 0.45 , respectively, showing standard to have the highest and variant A to have the lowest total fiber content. The iron (mg/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C was 4.06 ± 0.49 ; 6.41 ± 0.58 ; 5.91 ± 0.45 and 5.44 ± 0.33 , respectively, showing variant A to have the highest and standard to have the lowest iron content. The calcium (mg/100 g) content of standard, variant A, B and C was 68.97 ± 0.75 ; 65.93 ± 0.28 ; 78.87 ± 0.64 and 91.81 ± 0.48 , respectively, showing variant C to have the highest and variant A to have the lowest calcium content. The vitamin A ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g}$) content of standard, variant A, B and C were 0; 1592 ± 1.22 ; 1584 ± 0.91 and 1578 ± 0.88 , respectively, indicating variant A to have the highest content and standard to have no vitamin A present and retention was observed as 91%.

A paired t-test was conducted to analyze the nutrient content of each variant of chakli compared to standard chakli. A highly significant difference was seen in moisture, ash, carbohydrate, protein, fat, total fiber and vitamin A content, whereas a significant difference was observed in iron and calcium content of variant A. In variant B, a highly significant difference was seen in carbohydrate, protein, fat, total fiber and vitamin A content, whereas a significant difference was observed in moisture, ash, iron and calcium content. In variant C, a highly significant difference was seen in moisture, protein, fat, total fiber, and vitamin A content, whereas a significant difference was observed in ash, carbohydrates, iron and calcium content. It suggests that chakli variants (A, B, and C) have superior nutrient content compared to standard chakli. Furthermore, enriching all-purpose nutrient contents in the prepared chakli variants.

Table 3: Nutritional analysis of developed food products

Nutrients	Standard	Variant A	Variant B	Variant C
Moisture (g/100 g)	9.81 ± 0.05	$8.45 \pm 0.03^{**}$	$8.67 \pm 0.10^*$	$8.21 \pm 0.08^{**}$
Ash (g/100 g)	1.61 ± 0.04	$2.41 \pm 0.03^{**}$	$2.21 \pm 0.05^*$	$1.91 \pm 0.04^*$
Carbohydrate (g/100 g)	53.34 ± 0.23	$58.54 \pm 0.31^{**}$	$55.01 \pm 0.28^{**}$	$51.48 \pm 0.46^*$

Protein (g/100 g)	17.52±0.34	13.29±0.37**	13.66±0.44**	14.04±0.39**
Fat (g/100 g)	14.49±0.12	8.76±0.28**	9.45±0.23**	10.16±0.34**
Total fiber (g/100 g)	9.08±0.32	8.42±0.57**	8.74±0.22**	8.86±0.45**
Iron (mg/100 g)	4.06±0.49	6.41±0.58*	5.91±0.42*	5.44±0.33*
Calcium (mg/100 g)	68.97±0.75	65.93±0.28*	78.87±0.64*	91.81±0.48*
Vitamin A (µg/100 g)	Nil	1592±1.22**	1584±0.91**	1578±0.88**

Values are presented as means ± SD (n=3). Highly significant differences are denoted as ** (P <0.001), while significant differences are denoted as * (P <0.05)

Standard = 85 g all-purpose flour + 15 g butter	Variant A = 42 g all-purpose flour + 37 g black gram dal flour + 2 g flaxseed flour + 2 g sesame seeds + 15 g butter + 2 g nanoemulsion
Variant B = 42 g all-purpose flour + 37 g maize flour + 2 g flaxseed flour + 2 g sesame seeds + 15 g butter + 2 g nanoemulsion	Variant C = 42 g all-purpose flour + 37 g buckwheat flour + 2 g flaxseed flour + 2 g sesame seeds + 15 g butter + 2 g nanoemulsion

The nutritive composition analysis of the developed chakli variants revealed distinct variations in macronutrient and micronutrient profiles compared to the standard formulation. The reduced moisture content in all fortified variants compared to the standard suggests an improvement in shelf stability, which is in agreement with the findings of Singh et al. (2020), who reported that incorporation of composite flours tends to lower moisture content, thereby enhancing product storage potential. The increase in ash content, particularly in variant A, indicates a higher mineral content due to the incorporation of Bengal gram dal flour, flaxseed flour, and sesame seeds, which are known to be rich sources of minerals (Sharma et al., 2019).

The carbohydrate content was highest in variant A, which may be attributed to the high starch fraction of Bengal gram and flaxseed-based formulations, aligning with the results of Devi and Khatkar (2016), who noted that legume-enriched snacks often exhibit increased carbohydrate values. In contrast, the protein content was highest in the standard chakli, possibly because the replacement of all-purpose flour with other flours in the variants altered the protein composition. This observation partially agrees with the findings of Patil et al. (2021), who demonstrated that while legumes and oilseeds add protein, their overall protein contribution in baked/fried products can vary depending on processing and fat-binding effects.

The fat content reduction in variant A compared to the standard may be linked to the lower intrinsic fat levels of composite flours compared to refined wheat flour, as also observed by Verma et al. (2018) in oilseed and legume-based snack formulations. However, despite the fat reduction, total fiber content remained relatively high across all variants, supporting earlier reports by Rathi et al. (2017) that flaxseed and Bengal gram flour fortification significantly increases dietary fiber in snack foods.

Iron content was markedly higher in variant A compared to the standard, which can be directly associated with the mineral richness of Bengal gram dal and sesame seeds, consistent with the results of Gupta et al. (2015) in legume- and seed-based fortified snacks. Calcium content was

highest in variant C, most likely due to the contribution of sesame seeds, which are rich in bioavailable calcium, corroborating the observations of Bhat and Yahya (2014).

Notably, vitamin A content was present only in the fortified variants, with variant A exhibiting the highest value and a retention of 91%. This result highlights the stability of the nanoemulsion delivery system during product preparation and aligns with the findings of Ahmad et al. (2022), who reported high vitamin A retention in nanoemulsion-fortified bakery products even after thermal processing. This demonstrates that vitamin A nanoemulsions can effectively address micronutrient deficiencies while maintaining product sensory acceptability.

Overall, these results underscore the nutritional enhancement achieved through the incorporation of composite flours and vitamin A nanoemulsions, suggesting that such fortification strategies can be beneficial for developing nutrient-dense snack foods targeted at combating micronutrient malnutrition.

Conclusion

This study successfully developed a food-grade vitamin A nanoemulsion using a mixed surfactant system of Tween 80 and soya lecithin through ultrasonic homogenization. The formulation produced small, uniform droplets with good stability and high encapsulation efficiency, making it suitable for fortifying food products. Incorporation into chakli variants improved nutritional value and enhanced vitamin A content, with Variant A, enriched with Bengal gram dal flour, flaxseed flour, and sesame seeds, being the most preferred in sensory evaluation. While the study demonstrated promising results, it was limited to one type of food product, a short storage period, and did not assess large-scale production or vitamin A bioavailability. Future work should explore its application in a wider range of food and beverage systems, evaluate long-term stability, study bioavailability through in-vitro and in-vivo methods, and investigate its potential for delivering other fat-soluble vitamins or bioactive compounds.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to acknowledge the staff of Krishi Vigyan Kendra of Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India, for their support in the identification of the guava variety. We also want to give special thanks to Mr. Vimal Jain for giving us technical knowledge during our experiment.

Conflict of interest

No conflicts of interest are associated with the authors for this investigation.

References

1. Ahmad, M., Ashraf, M. A., Gani, A., & Masoodi, F. A. Encapsulation of vitamin A in nanoemulsions for food fortification: Stability and retention during processing. *Food Chemistry*. 2022;372, 131302.
2. Algahtani MS, Ahmad MZ, Ahmad J. Nanoemulgel for improved topical delivery of retinyl palmitate: formulation design and stability evaluation. *Nanomaterials*. 2020 Apr 28;10(5):848.
3. Almeida, A. F., Borsarelli, C. D., & Mercadante, A. Z. Encapsulation of bioactive compounds for food application: a review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*. 2019;90, 85–95.
4. Argimón M, Romero M, Miranda P, Mombrú ÁW, Miraballes I, Zimet P, Pardo H. Development and characterization of vitamin A-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles for topical application. *Journal of the Brazilian chemical society*. 2017 Jul;28(07):1177-84.
5. Bhat, R., & Yahya, N. Nutritional quality of selected traditional snacks from Malaysia. *International Food Research Journal*. 2014;21(2), 617–622.
6. Boskabadi M, Saeedi M, Akbari J, Morteza-Semnani K, Hashemi SM, Babaei A. Topical gel of vitamin A solid lipid nanoparticles: a hopeful promise as a dermal delivery system. *Advanced Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2020 Oct 3;11(4):663.
7. Das AK, Nanda PK, Bandyopadhyay S, Banerjee R, Biswas S, McClements DJ. Application of nanoemulsion-based approaches for improving the quality and safety of muscle foods: A comprehensive review. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*. 2020;19(5):2677-2700.
8. Devi, A., & Khatkar, B. S. Physicochemical, functional and nutritional characteristics of wheat, maize and chickpea flours. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2016;53(1), 445–453.

9. Elarbi FM, Ettarhouni ZO, Abdussalam-Mohammed W, Mezoughi AB. Study on the Effects of Biologically Active Amino Acids on the Micellization of Anionic Surfactant Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS) at Different Temperatures. *Chemistry*. 2022;4(1):146-155.
10. Gupta, S., Lakshmi, A. J., & Prakash, J. In vitro bioavailability of calcium and iron from selected green leafy vegetables. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*. 2015;95(9), 1983–1989.
11. Hassan ME, Hassan RR, Diab KA, El-Nekeety AA, Hassan NS, Abdel-Wahhab MA. Nanoencapsulation of thyme essential oil: a new avenue to enhance its protective role against oxidative stress and cytotoxicity of zinc oxide nanoparticles in rats. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2021 Oct;28(37):52046-63.
12. Jun, S. H., Kim, H., Lee, H., Song, J. E., Park, S. G., & Kang, N. G. (2021). Synthesis of retinol-loaded lipid nanocarrier via vacuum emulsification to improve topical skin delivery. *Polymers*, 13(5), 826.
13. Kim TI, Kim TG, Lim DH, Kim SB, Park SM, Hur TY, Ki KS, Kwon EG, Vijayakumar M, Kim YJ. Preparation of nanoemulsions of Vitamin A and C by microfluidization: Efficacy on the expression pattern of milk-specific proteins in MAC-T cells. *Molecules*. 2019 Jul 15;24(14):2566.
14. Kundu S, Rai B, Shukla A. Prevalence and determinants of Vitamin A deficiency among children in India: Findings from a national cross-sectional survey. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*. 2021;11:1-7.
15. Mehmood T, Ahmed A, Ahmed Z, Ahmad MS. Optimization of soya lecithin and Tween 80 based novel vitamin D nanoemulsions prepared by ultrasonication using response surface methodology. *Food Chemistry*. 2019 Aug 15;289:664-70.
16. Mehmood T. Optimization of the canola oil based vitamin E nanoemulsions stabilized by food grade mixed surfactants using response surface methodology. *Food Chemistry*. 2015 Sep 15;183:1-7.
17. Mujica-Álvarez J, Gil-Castell O, Barra PA, Ribes-Greus A, Bustos R, Faccini M, Matiacevich S. Encapsulation of vitamins A and E as spray-dried additives for the feed industry. *Molecules*. 2020 Mar 17;25(6):1357.
18. Mun S, Kim YR, McClements DJ. Control of β -carotene bioaccessibility using starch-based filled hydrogels. *Food chemistry*. 2015;173:454-461.
19. NIN. A manual of laboratory techniques. Hyderabad, National Institute of Nutrition, Indian Council of Medical Research. 2003.
20. Patel, A., Sharma, A., & Sahu, J. K. Development and quality evaluation of protein and mineral enriched ready-to-eat extruded snacks. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2021;58(4), 1213–1222.
21. Patil, S., Rathod, P., & Kulkarni, A. Nutritional and sensory characteristics of legume-based extruded products. *Legume Science*. 2021;3(3), e79.
22. Raghuramulu N, Nair KM, Kalyanasundaram S. A Manual of Laboratory Techniques (2nd edition). National Institute of Nutrition-Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), 2003.
23. Rathi, A., Kawatra, A., & Sehgal, S. Development and nutritional evaluation of high-protein, high-fibre and low-fat snacks using flaxseed and bengal gram flour. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2017;54(4), 921–927.
24. Sahoo M, Vishwakarma S, Panigrahi C, Kumar J. Nanotechnology: Current applications and future scope in food. *Food Frontiers*. 2021;2(1):3-22.
25. Samal D. Use of nanotechnology in food industry: a review. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology*. 2017;2(4):2270-2278.
26. Sarkar A, Murray B, Holmes M, Ettelaie R, Abdalla A, Yang X. In vitro digestion of Pickering emulsions stabilized by soft whey protein microgel particles: influence of thermal treatment. *Soft Matter*. 2016;12(15):3558-69.
27. Sharma, S., Gupta, N., & Chauhan, E. S. Nutritional evaluation of flaxseed and sesame seed incorporated products. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*. 2019;8(3), 1221–1230.
28. Singh, R., Kaur, A., & Manan, J. K. Influence of composite flour blends on physicochemical and nutritional properties of extruded snacks. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2020;57(9), 3270–3280.
29. Verma, A., Sharma, B., & Arora, S. Nutritional and sensory attributes of snacks enriched with oilseeds. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*. 2019;42(2), e13483.